

RESTORE

Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage
Technology in Order to Raise Economic and
environmental sustainability of DHC

D5.9 - Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case VI: Small scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano Campus

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036766.

PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET	
Project Acronym	RESTORE
Project Full Title	Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Environmental sustainability of DHC
Grant Agreement	101036766
Call Identifier	H2020-LC-GD-2020-1
Topic	Innovative land-based and offshore renewable energy technologies and their integration into the energy system
Project Duration	48 months (October 2021 – September 2025)
Project Website	www.restore-dhc.eu
Disclaimer	The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the funding authorities. The funding authorities are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION SHEET	
Number	Deliverable D5.9
Full Title	Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case VI: Small-scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus
Related WP	WP5
Related Task	Task T5.4: Implementation, optimization, management & validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform Sub-Task 5.4.6: Use-Case VI - Small scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus
Lead Beneficiary	CENER
Author(s)	Marco Astolfi (POLIMI) - marco.astolfi@polimi.it Dario Alfani (POLIMI) - dario.alfani@polimi.it
Contributor(s)	Riccardo Simonetti (POLIMI) – riccardo.simonetti@polimi.it Abdullah Bamoshmoosh (POLIMI) - abdullah.bamoshmoosh@polimi.it Antonino Ravidà (POLIMI) – antonino.ravida@polimi.it Giovanni Gustavo Lozza (POLIMI) - giovanni.lozza@polimi.it Stefan Bergmann (SimTech) - s.bergmann@simtechnology.com
Reviewer(s)	Francisco Cabello Nuñez (CENER) - fcabello@cener.com Fatima Dargam (SIMTECH) - f.dargam@simtechnology.com
Dissemination level	Public
Due Date	July 2025
Submission Date	August 1st, 2025
Status	Final

QUALITY CONTROL ASSESSMENT SHEET			
ISSUE	DATE	COMMENT	AUTHOR
V0.1	10/07/2025	Draft_Version 01	Marco Astolfi (POLIMI) Dario Alfani (POLIMI)
V0.2	20/07/2025	Reviewed Version	Riccardo Simonetti (POLIMI) Abdullah Bamoshmoosh (POLIMI) Antonino Ravidà (POLIMI) Giovanni Gustavo Lozza (POLIMI) Stefan Bergmann (SimTech)
V0.2	28/07/2025	Draft_Version 02	Marco Astolfi (POLIMI) Dario Alfani (POLIMI) Riccardo Simonetti (POLIMI) Abdullah Bamoshmoosh (POLIMI)
V0.3	31/07/2025	Reviewed Version	Fatima Dargam (SIMTECH) Stefan Bergmann (SimTech)
V1.0	31/07/2025	Final Version	Marco Astolfi (POLIMI) Dario Alfani (POLIMI)
V1.0	01/08/2025	Review + Submission to the EC	Francisco Cabello Nuñez (CENER)

Summary

This deliverable presents the activities and outcomes of Task 5.4 within RESTORE EU project, which focuses on demonstrating the performance and replicability of the RESTORE integrated system in several facilities. The task consists of the implementation, optimization, and validation of six real use-cases through their digital representations, using the RESTORE Simulation Web Platform (IPSE GO). These virtual models aim to replicate real district heating and cooling (DHC) networks across diverse industrial and geographical contexts in Europe, including biomass and solar systems, cement and paper industries, steelworks, geothermal applications, and university campuses.

Deliverable D5.9 deals with the implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case VI: Small-scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus.

The document details the methodological framework used to implement the Use-Case VI (related to Sub-task T5.4.6), drawing on technical input from WP1 to WP5, and presenting simulation models for Use-Case VI, also within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, resulting from the integration of the RESTORE concept coupled to a small campus DHC. For the use-case, the partners defined specific system boundaries, components, and operational conditions, which were then simulated and optimized in ad hoc developed numerical tools and subsequently in the platform. The work provides a technical validation of the RESTORE concept including economic preliminary evaluations and a structured dataset to support environmental impact assessment. Ultimately, the insights gathered here serve as a cornerstone for developing small-scale replication strategies in Task 5.5, facilitating broader deployment of RESTORE technologies across Europe.

Further information about economic analysis of this use case will be included in the deliverable D1.9 “Report on the assessment of the socio-economic sustainability (V2 final)”.

Table of Contents

Summary	4
Table of Contents	5
1. Introduction	7
2. Baseline Plant.....	8
2.1. Plant description: POLIMI campus energy network.....	8
2.1.1. Electrical and Thermal Demand.....	9
2.1.1.1. Combined Heat and Power Unit.....	11
2.1.1.1.1. Natural gas boilers	12
2.1.1.1.2. Absorption chiller	12
2.2. Modelling of plant components.....	13
2.2.1. CHP unit.....	14
2.2.1.1. CHP unit electrical performance.....	14
2.2.1.2. CHP unit thermal performance.....	15
2.2.2. Natural gas boilers.....	17
2.2.3. Absorption chiller	18
2.2.4. Numerical models validation on a reference year	19
2.3. Cost and Incentives.....	22
2.4. Optimization of baseline system operation	23
2.4.1. CHP management strategy	23
2.4.2. CHP optimal manamegement strategy	26
2.4.2.1. Possibility to sell electricity to the grid	27
2.4.2.1.1. Results post-processing.....	27
2.4.2.1.2. Effect of $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ on optimization results	28
2.4.3. Yearly Optimal Control Mode Distribution	28
2.4.4. Results of optimal control strategy.....	30
2.4.4.1. Typical Week Analysis	33
2.4.5. Optimization of PV-integrated system operation	35
2.4.5.1. PV system integration	35
2.4.5.1.1. CHP operating strategy modificatios	36
2.4.6. PV-integrated results and optimal control distribution	37
3. RESTORE TCES Integration.....	40
3.1. User Case definition	41
3.1.1. Preliminary analysis of seasonal TCES integration.....	41
3.1.1.1. Modelling Assumptions	41

- 3.1.1.2. Results of seasonal TCES integration43
- 3.1.2. Preliminary analysis of daily TCES integration.....46
- 3.1. Representing Use-Case VI in the IPSE GO Platform49
- 3.2. Input Data.....50
 - 3.2.1. Assumptions.....50
- 3.3. IPSE GO Virtual Case implementation.....51
 - 3.3.1. UC6 Model definition51
 - 3.3.2. The Charging Mode.....53
 - 3.3.3. The Discharging Mode.....55
- 4. Results..... 58
 - 4.1. Process Simulations.....58
 - 4.1.1. The Charging Mode.....58
 - 4.1.2. The Discharging Mode60
- 5. Conclusions 63
- 6. References 64

1. Introduction

Subtask 5.4.6 (Use-Case VI - Small scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus) addresses the implementation and virtual replication of the RESTORE TCES concept within a district heating network in the Politecnico di Milano campus. This facility combines natural gas boilers, a Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit and absorption chiller to supply electricity, heating and cooling demands. The objective is to integrate these technologies into the RESTORE concept and to build the simulation framework to assess the storage performance under different operational conditions and control strategies.

Led by POLIMI, with the technical support of SIMTECH for the development of IPSE GO simulation model, the work involves defining the system mass and energy balances integration, the definition of available renewable energy sources and thermal chemical energy storage (TCES) configuration. The model implemented using different programming efforts, and also is implemented within the IPSE GO platform, enabling interactive simulation, control testing, and optimization of system sizing and parameters involved. Additionally, a dedicated economic and financial evaluation outlines the indicators to be evaluated.

This document is structured to present a comprehensive analysis of the implementation of the User Case VI. It begins with a description of the baseline plant, including its technical background and configuration (Section 2). Section 3 focuses on the integration of the RESTORE TCES system, detailing the use-case definition, the role of the IPSE GO Platform, the input data (including assumptions and refinements), and the virtual implementation steps. Section 4 presents the results, focusing on process simulations results and quantification of system volume.

2. Baseline Plant

This chapter focuses on the description of the existing system, its components and the available data. It is split into different sections dealing with:

- (2.1) the description of POLIMI Campus local district heating and cooling network, including trends of electric and thermal demand and description of main components based on information from datasheet
- (2.2) the analysis of field data to calibrate performance functions for each component to be used for the numerical analysis of the system
- (2.3) an analysis of the incentives and subsidies framework granted by Italy for high efficiency cogeneration
- (2.4) the optimization of the system operation in the reference year and the impact of local PV integration

General information about this Use-Case and its plant, is also described in the public documentation of “RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling” concerning WP5 Task T5.4 implementation, optimization, management & validation of the six RESTORE Use-Cases, using the Simulation Web Platform”, available in the project’s Zenodo Community account (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/records>).” [1]

2.1. Plant description: POLIMI campus energy network

In 2015, Politecnico di Milano inaugurated PoliGrid, an advanced energy network designed to optimize the energy production, consumption and distribution in the Leonardo campus. It connects over 25 campus buildings through a medium-voltage 23 kV network, supplying electricity primarily through self-generation from a cogeneration unit and a photovoltaic (PV) plant installed on the buildings rooftops. When the campus electrical demand exceeds the internal production, the required additional electricity is provided from the distribution electrical grid.

The core of PoliGrid consists of a 2 MW electric cogeneration plant, which produces both electricity and heat with an overall efficiency exceeding 82%, supplying a 2-kilometer-long district heating loop. In summer, the system shifts to trigeneration, using waste heat to drive an absorption chiller that delivers 1.4 MW of cooling to selected buildings. Backup natural gas boilers are activated when the thermal demand surpasses the capacity of the cogeneration unit. The microgrid also integrates renewable energy through a network of rooftop photovoltaic systems, already reaching 1 MW of installed capacity and expected to grow.

Figure 1. Electrical and thermal network of Politecnico di Milano.

2.1.1. Electrical and Thermal Demand

The energy demand of Leonardo campus of Politecnico di Milano exhibits significant variability throughout the year, driven by seasonal fluctuations and the academic calendar, which includes teaching periods, exam sessions, and holiday breaks. On an annual basis, the campus consumes approximately 14 GWh of electricity and 11 GWh of thermal energy, corresponding to a total natural gas consumption of about 3.3 million cubic meters.

Figure 2. Weekly energy consumption profiles throughout the year.

As shown in [Figure 2](#), January, February, and December exhibit the highest thermal demand, with peak values exceeding 600 MWh. Thermal demand then declines significantly, reaching its first minimum in April and May, where values approach zero. During this period, as well as in October, neither heating nor cooling is required, as external temperatures remain within a moderate range.

Subsequently, thermal demand increases during the summer months, driven by the need for chilled water. This demand is met by converting the thermal energy produced by the power plant into cooling energy.

Regarding electrical demand, the highest consumption occurs in July, with weekly requirements peaking at 400 MWh. However, electrical demand is generally more stable throughout the year compared to thermal demand, with the exception of notable fluctuations at the beginning of January and during the summer months.

All the instantaneous quantities (such as water mass flow rates, temperatures, thermal and electrical powers, etc.) are measured and are made available on request through an online platform (<https://www.commissionenergia.polimi.it/poligrd/>).

The data is provided as 1-hour aggregates, offering sufficient temporal resolution to capture thermal and electrical production and demand patterns across day and night cycles, weekdays and holidays, and seasonal variations such as winter and summer.

Figure 3. Weekly energy consumption profiles throughout the year.

Figure 4. Sample of DH thermal demand of POLIMI campus.

2.1.1.1. Combined Heat and Power Unit

The Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit is fuelled by natural gas and simultaneously produces electricity and thermal energy by recovering the heat that would otherwise be lost through the release of high temperature flue gases to the environment. This cogeneration process significantly improves overall energy efficiency, reducing energy waste, lowering operational costs, and minimizing emissions.

In this study, the CHP model is a Jenbacher JMS 612 GS-N.L. gas engine, with a nominal electrical output of 2,000 kW_{el}. Electricity is generated directly through the combustion of natural gas, while heat is recovered from the engine oil, cooling water, and exhaust gases, whose temperatures are reduced from approximately 350°C to 120°C. The system also includes a diverter valve, which adjusts the quantity of thermal energy recovered by modulating the flow of exhaust gases.

The main rated parameters of the CHP unit are listed in Table 1. These specifications, provided by the Energy Commission of Politecnico di Milano, reflect the nameplate data of the equipment.

For the purpose of this analysis, it is assumed that the CHP unit operates continuously on an hourly basis, without intermittent start-stop cycling. Therefore, the system cannot operate below its minimum load.

Table 1. Main parameters of the CHP unit.

Parameter	100% Load	75% Load	50% Load
Gas Flow Rate [Nm ³ /h]	485	374	260
Nominal Electrical Power [kW _{el}]	2000	1498	990
Electrical Efficiency	0.434	0.422	0.397
Max Recoverable Thermal Power [kW]	1791	1439	1054
Thermal Efficiency	0.389	0.405	0.423

Figure 5. Jenbacher JMS 612 GS-N.L. combined heat and power engine.

2.1.1.1. Natural gas boilers

Two ICI TNOX.e boilers, each with a nominal thermal power of 6,000 kW, are installed in the plant. These boilers are activated when the thermal demand exceeds the heat output of the CHP unit. Unlike the CHP, the boilers can operate intermittently, cycling on and off multiple times within an hour, and thus do not have a minimum power limit.

Table 2. Main parameters of the natural gas boilers.

Parameter	Value
Nominal Thermal Power [kW]	6,000
Efficiency	0.951

The boilers are designed to remain off during the summer period when thermal demand is low, as they are not connected to the absorption chiller for cooling purposes. However, this study also considers a scenario where the boilers are integrated with the absorption chiller as part of a further analysis.

Figure 6. ICI TNOX.e natural gas boilers.

2.1.1.2. Absorption chiller

The cogeneration unit is connected to an LG model LWM-123ET single-effect water- lithium bromide absorption chiller with a nominal capacity of 1,433 kW. This chiller produces chilled water during the summer by utilizing heat recovered from the CHP, ensuring efficient energy utilization throughout the year.

However, it is important to note that these nameplate data are based on tests conducted by the manufacturer under specific operating conditions, which differ from those at the PoliMi campus. For instance, the actual operating temperatures deviate from the values specified in the datasheet, leading to variations in energy production and efficiency.

Table 3. Main parameters of the absorption chiller.

Parameter	Value
Nominal Input Thermal Power [kW]	1,790
Nominal Cooling Power [kW]	1,433

This aspect will be further examined in the next section, where adjustments to the nominal values are applied to accurately model each component and correctly simulate the measured data for the reference year provided by POLIMI Energy Commission.

Figure 7. LG model LWM-123ET single-effect water- lithium bromide absorption chiller.

2.2. Modelling of plant components

To assess the impact of integrating renewable energy sources (RES) and the RESTORE energy storage into the system, it is crucial to develop numerical models that accurately represent the operational behavior of the CHP unit, the natural gas boilers and the absorption chiller. For this purpose, hourly data from year 2023 are used as the reference dataset. The reference data, measured directly by POLIMI Energy Commission, include:

- Natural gas consumption by the CHP [Nm^3/h],
- Electrical and thermal energy produced by the CHP [kWh],
- Natural gas consumption by the boilers [Nm^3/h],
- Thermal energy produced by the boilers [kWh],
- Cooling energy produced by the absorption chiller [kWh],
- Electric energy purchased and fed into the grid [kWh].

By leveraging these data alongside the specifications provided in the technical datasheets, the operational characteristics of the system components can be modeled through the development of efficiency curves that establish the correlation between input energy and output energy for each component.

2.2.1. CHP unit

2.2.1.1. CHP unit electrical performance

The numerical model of the CHP unit has the objective to estimate the natural gas consumption of the CHP unit based on its electrical output, using the following relationship:

$$E_{el,h} = m_{NG,h} \cdot LHV_{NG} \cdot \eta_{el,CHP}(m_{NG,h})$$

where:

- $m_{NG,h}$ is the hourly natural gas consumption,
- LHV_{NG} is the Lower Heating Value of natural gas equal to 9.5 kWh/m³,
- $\eta_{el,CHP}$ is the electrical efficiency of the CHP, which is a function of the natural gas flow rate.

The electrical efficiency curve is constructed from the data of Table 1, which provides efficiency values at three operating points: 100% load (maximum flow rate), 75% load, and 50% load (minimum flow rate).

A quadratic interpolation of these points yields the following efficiency function:

$$\eta_{el,CHP} = -6.4 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot m_{NG}^2 + 6.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot m_{NG} + 0.265$$

The obtained curve is then validated against measured data to assess its accuracy in representing the actual electrical performance of the CHP. To improve accuracy, outliers and measurement errors are removed, and the analysis is restricted to the following operational ranges:

- Gas consumption between 260 Nm³/h (minimum) and 485 Nm³/h (maximum),
- Electrical output between 0 kW_{el} and 2000 kW_{el},
- Electrical efficiency constrained between 35% and 52% to exclude anomalies.

The accuracy of the theoretical curve is evaluated using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and the results yield an MSE of 0.0004 and an MAE of 0.0129, indicating that the interpolated curve provides a reliable approximation of the measured efficiency values. Accordingly, this curve is then adopted to model the electrical performance of the CHP. [Figure 8](#) shows the comparison between the obtained numerical correlation and the measured data.

Figure 8. CHP electrical efficiency vs natural gas flow rate: comparison between the obtained numerical correlation and the measured data.

2.2.1.2. CHP unit thermal performance

As with electrical efficiency, the objective is to establish a correlation between the thermal efficiency of the cogeneration unit and the natural gas flow rate.

However, due to lower return water temperatures on campus compared to those used during standard performance testing, the system is able to recover a greater amount of thermal energy. Consequently, the datasheet values tend to underestimate the actual thermal performance and cannot be directly applied. For this reason, the efficiency curve is derived from experimental data, with hourly thermal efficiency calculated using the following expression:

$$\eta_{th,CHP} = \frac{E_{th,measured}}{m_{NG,measured} \cdot LHV_{NG}}$$

The obtained data are subsequently filtered to eliminate outliers and measurement errors, with the analysis limited to the following operational ranges:

- Gas consumption between 260 Nm³/h and 485 Nm³/h,
- Thermal power recovery between 0 kW and 2200 kW,
- Thermal efficiency between 0% and 52%.

An additional complexity is related to the presence of a diverter, which can bypass part of the exhaust gases. As a result, for a given natural gas flow rate, thermal efficiency values can vary significantly depending on the amount of heat effectively recovered.

To account for this variability, the thermal efficiency curve is constructed by fitting the upper envelope of the measured data, as shown in [Figure 9](#). This envelope is obtained using a piecewise spline interpolation, capturing the maximum recoverable thermal performance across the operating range.

Figure 9. Envelope curve of the CHP thermal efficiency vs the natural gas mass flow rate (filtered data).

The two curves describing the CHP electrical and thermal performance, respectively, are represented in [Figure 10](#).

Figure 10. CHP electrical and thermal efficiencies as a function of the NG flow rate

2.2.2. Natural gas boilers

In contrast to the CHP unit, the thermal efficiency of the boilers is assumed to remain constant, independent of the gas flow rate.

Additionally, since both boilers display nearly identical performance, they are modeled as a single unit with a nominal thermal capacity of 12 MW.

As with the CHP, the lower return water temperatures observed on campus - compared to those used during standard performance testing - result in actual efficiencies that exceed the datasheet values.

For this reason, the boiler thermal efficiency is defined as:

$$\eta_{th,boiler} = 0.98$$

This value is selected because it minimizes the discrepancy with the results obtained from the measured annual gas consumption. Given the high variability in the hourly data, the measurements are aggregated into daily averages to improve clarity and interpretability, and are here reported in [Figure 11](#)~~Figure 14~~.

The results indicate that the MSE is 0.0009, while the MAE is 0.0219.

It must be noted that the MAE indicates a non-negligible level of deviation of the numerical model results, as the mean absolute difference is approximately 2 percentage points. However, as will be demonstrated in Section 2.2.4, this does not significantly impact the overall results, leading to a relatively small error between the overall PoliGrid model and the actual measured data.

Figure 11. Daily averages of boiler efficiency vs natural gas consumption.

2.2.3. Absorption chiller

The aim in this case is to define the relationship between the cooling energy produced by the absorption chiller and the thermal energy supplied to this component. Specifically, the objective is to determine the chiller's Coefficient of Performance (COP) as a function of the thermal input. This relationship is expressed as:

$$E_{cooling,h} = E_{th,input,h} \cdot COP(E_{th,input,h})$$

As the COP curve is not available in the datasheet, it is derived from measured operational data. A second-degree polynomial interpolation is used to construct the curve, as shown in [Figure 12](#). The measured data reveal a plateau in performance for thermal energy inputs around 1000 kW_{th}. Consequently, from the identified maximum point at (1071 kW_{th}, 0.67), the COP is considered constant to reflect the chiller's saturation behavior.

Figure 12. Hourly average COP of the absorption chiller vs the thermal energy input: comparison between the obtained numerical correlation and the measured data.

The resulting curve presents a MSE of 0.0097 and a MAE of 0.0687, indicating a moderate deviation from the hourly measurements. Nonetheless, even in this case, as demonstrated in Section 2.2.4, the effect of these discrepancies on annual energy balance calculations is negligible. The total annual error remains within acceptable bounds, confirming that the constructed COP curve provides a reliable basis for system-level analysis.

The COP curve is defined by the following expression:

$$COP_{chiller} = \begin{cases} -7 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot E_{th,input}^2 + 0.0015 \cdot E_{th,input} - 0.1338, & \text{if } E_{th,input} < 1071 \text{ kW}_{th} \\ 0.67, & \text{if } E_{th,input} \geq 1071 \text{ kW}_{th} \end{cases}$$

2.2.4. Numerical models validation on a reference year

With the component-specific performance models established, a comprehensive simulation framework is developed. This model serves as the reference for subsequent analyses and is designed to closely replicate the 2023 operational data provided by POLIMI Energy Commission. Its purpose is to validate the accuracy of the implemented efficiency curves and system behavior assumptions.

Given the inherent uncertainties in measured data resulting from sensor precision, suboptimal conditions, and environmental variability, the model is considered accurate if its annual outputs align with the aggregate measured values. As shown in Section 2.2.4, discrepancies at the monthly level are limited, suggesting that the developed model offers a reliable representation of real operation.

The model operates on an hourly basis, following a structured sequence:

- i) First, if the CHP unit was inactive during a given hour in 2023, it is also deactivated in the model.
- ii) The corresponding natural gas flow rate is calculated iteratively from the measured electrical output, accounting for the dependency of electrical efficiency on gas consumption.

$$m_{NG,CHP,h} = \frac{E_{el,CHP,h}}{\eta_{el,CHP}(m_{NG,CHP,h}) \cdot LHV_{NG}}$$

- iii) From this, the maximum recoverable thermal energy is computed.

$$E_{th,CHP,max,h} = m_{NG,CHP,h} \cdot LHV_{NG} \cdot \eta_{th,CHP}(m_{NG,CHP,h})$$

- iv) Then, the actual thermal energy extracted is determined by comparing it to the measured demand, considering the operation of the diverter valve.

$$E_{th,CHP,h} = \min(E_{th,CHP,max,h}; E_{th,CHP,measured,h})$$

- v) During the cooling season - from May 17th to September 30th - the model checks whether the chiller is active. If so, it estimates the thermal input required to meet the cooling load using the COP curve, and adjusts the recovered heat accordingly.

$$E_{th,input,h} = \frac{D_{cooling,h}}{COP(E_{th,input,h})}$$

$$E_{th,CHP,h} = \min(E_{th,CHP,max,h}; E_{th,input,h})$$

- vi) The remaining thermal demand, not met by the CHP, is satisfied by the boilers.

$$E_{th,boiler,h} = D_{thermal,h} - E_{th,CHP,h}$$

- vii) Boiler natural gas consumption is then calculated using the assumed constant thermal efficiency.

$$m_{NG,boiler,h} = \frac{E_{th,boiler,h}}{LHV_{NG} \cdot \eta_{boiler}}$$

The model’s performance is validated by comparing annual outputs with measured data. For 2023, the deviation in CHP gas consumption is -1.8%, while the CHP thermal energy shows a deviation of -1%.

Although a small number of hourly values exceed the theoretical thermal recovery limit, these are attributed to measurement anomalies or COP overestimations. The absorption chiller model shows zero error on an annual basis, with only minor monthly fluctuations, in particular for the month of June and July.

The boiler model deviates by just 1% in terms of thermal output and 3% in gas consumption, confirming the reliability of the adopted efficiency value.

Figure 13. CHP monthly natural gas consumption trend in the developed numerical model and in the measured data

Figure 14. CHP monthly thermal energy trend in the developed numerical model and in the measured data

Figure 15. Monthly thermal demand trend in the developed numerical model and in the measured data

Figure 16. Monthly boiler natural gas consumption trend in the developed numerical model and in the measured data

Further validation is conducted using 2024 data, after correcting for known measurement anomalies - such as incomplete hourly records in February and missing natural gas flow values in September. Overall, the model maintains strong alignment with measured results, with deviations across all subsystems remaining within $\pm 5\%$.

Notably, the largest gap is in boiler natural gas consumption, but this discrepancy also includes the effect of errors in the estimated boiler thermal output. Despite these differences, the developed numerical model accurately captures the integrated behavior of the energy system and is suitable for use in the optimization analyses proposed in the next sections of this deliverable. Also, the results of this model will be called reference case and used as benchmark for further improvements in the management of the POLIMI campus cogeneration unit from a techno-economic perspective.

2.3. Cost and Incentives

The optimization of cogeneration systems must balance energy efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and emissions reduction, while leveraging available incentive mechanisms. The economic analysis includes fuel and electricity costs, revenues from TEE (Energy Efficiency Certificates or White Certificates) and CO₂ emissions (Scopes 1–3).

Gas and electricity prices are considered as time-dependent, and the following economic assumptions are used:

- Electricity is purchased at PUN (Prezzo Unico Nazionale).
- Exported electricity is sold at PZ (Prezzo Zonale Nord), due to ineligibility for SSP (Scambio sul Posto) since the plant exceeds 200 kW_e.
- Natural gas is purchased at PSV (Punto di Scambio Virtuale).
- Electricity fed into the grid receives no additional incentives due to the plant already benefiting from TEE.
- Contractual exemptions for large consumers (e.g., Politecnico di Milano) allow the exclusion of taxes and distribution fees in the analysis.
- No carbon tax is considered, as this is not applied in Italy, and the plant likely qualifies for ETS exemption (thermal capacity <35 MW, emissions <25,000 tCO₂/y).
- TEEs are valued at €250/certificate, based on recent market stabilization.

Regarding the TEE Incentives (in Italian Certificati Bianchi), DL 5/9/2011 state that plants that meet CAR (High Efficiency Cogeneration, in Italian Cogenerazione ad Alto Rendimento) standards can earn TEE. CAR compliance requires:

- Primary Energy Saving (PES) ≥ 10% (for units >1 MW_e).
- Global efficiency > 75% (electrical + thermal output / fuel input).

If this last condition is met, all the electricity produced is classified as cogeneration. Conversely, if this threshold is not reached, the concept of “virtual machine” is used to isolate the cogenerated share of electricity.

Once CAR compliance is verified, the number of TEEs will be equal to:

$$TEE = RISP \cdot 0.086 \cdot K$$

Where the actual primary energy savings (RISP) must be calculated as:

$$RISP = \frac{E_{CHP}}{\eta_{el,ref,ITA}} + \frac{H_{CHP}}{\eta_{th,ref,ITA}} - F_{CHP}$$

Where K depends on the plant's average electrical power during the year, F_{CHP} is the portion of fuel energy into the system that participates in the cogeneration process, E_{CHP} and H_{CHP} are the electric and thermal energy produced by the virtual machine.

Regarding CO₂ emissions, these are computed as:

- Scope 1 (direct), which are calculated using a national CO₂ emission factor for gas, equal to 1.956 kg/m³.

- Scope 2 (indirect – grid imports), which are based on Italian grid emission factor, equal to 0.2356 kg/kWh.
- Scope 3 (avoided emissions), which are negative values representing avoided emissions thanks to more efficient cogeneration vs. national grid mix.

2.4. Optimization of baseline system operation

2.4.1. CHP management strategy

Heuristic models are practical methods designed to tackle complex decision-making problems using simplifications, rule-based logic, or experience-based rules. While they may not guarantee an optimal solution, they deliver sufficiently accurate results within manageable computational effort - especially useful in contexts with large decision spaces, incomplete data, or high levels of uncertainty.

In this context, for a preliminary optimization of the CHP operation apply it has been decided to apply heuristic formulations focusing on two traditional control modes: thermal-load-following and electrical-load-following.

In thermal-load-following mode, the CHP is dispatched to satisfy the hourly thermal demand. It generates electricity as a byproduct: any surplus electrical power is exported to the grid, and any shortfall is procured as purchases.

In electrical-load-following mode, the CHP targets the hourly electrical demand. The recovered heat is regulated via a diverter: excess heat is bypassed, while any thermal deficit is met by boilers.

To evaluate operational performance and cost efficiency, seven different heuristic scenarios are compared:

- **Scenario 1:** Thermal-load-following; CHP runs at minimum load when thermal demand is below the minimum.
- **Scenario 2:** Same as Scenario 1, but CHP is turned off when thermal demand is below the minimum - except during the cooling season when the chiller is active.
- **Scenario 3:** Similar to Scenario 2, but assumes the boiler can directly supply thermal energy for chiller operation; thus the CHP can remain off even in hot periods.
- **Scenario 4:** Electrical-load-following; CHP operates at minimum load when electrical demand is below the minimum.
- **Scenario 5:** Electrical-load-following; CHP is completely shut down when electrical demand falls below the minimum.
- **Scenario 6:** CHP remains off year-round; boilers and the electricity grid fulfill all demand.
- **Scenario 7:** CHP runs at full load continuously, maximizing electricity sales to the grid; excess heat is dumped via the diverter.

The input data for the model are defined as follows:

- Hourly electrical demand $D_{electrical}$,
- Hourly thermal demand $D_{thermal}$,
- Hourly cooling demand $D_{cooling}$ when the absorption chiller is switched on,
- Hourly PUN (Prezzo Unico Nazionale),
- Hourly PZ (Prezzo Zonale),
- Hourly PSV (Punto di Scambio Virtuale).

Figure 17. Comparison of the total gas consumption and its cost, electricity withdrawn from the grid and its cost, PES and TEE revenues for the different scenarios results with respect to the reference case.

Figure 18. Comparison of the total cost variation for the different scenarios results with respect to the reference case.

As shown in [Figure 17](#) and [Figure 18](#), each scenario yields different outcomes compared to the reference one, with some metrics improving and others deteriorating.

Thermal-load-following scenarios (Scenarios 1–3) lead to a substantial reduction in total natural gas consumption, with values around -45% in Scenario 3. This is largely due to the lower annual thermal energy demand relative to electricity demand, and the large number of hours with zero thermal load but sustained electrical demand. A 30% difference in gas consumption reduction is observed between Scenario 1 and Scenario 3, mainly due to variations in CHP operating hours. In Scenarios 2 and 3, the CHP unit is shut down whenever demand falls below its minimum load threshold. While this increases boiler usage, the overall gas consumption remains lower thanks to the higher efficiency of the boilers.

In contrast, electrical-load-following scenarios (Scenarios 4 and 5) result in higher gas consumption. Since electricity demand is more stable and never drops to zero, CHP operating hours increase, leading to more natural gas consumption. Interestingly, Scenarios 4 and 5 exhibit identical gas consumption, as they share the same CHP operating schedule.

Reducing CHP operating hours has mixed consequences. On the one hand, it lowers natural gas usage and costs. On the other, it leads to a significant increase in electricity purchased from the grid, as the CHP is no longer available to cover electrical demand, thus driving up total electricity costs. As a result, thermal-load-following scenarios exhibit higher electricity purchases and costs compared to electrical-load-following scenarios, which benefit from increased CHP operation relative to the reference case.

Scenario 6, in which the CHP is completely removed, exhibits the lowest gas consumption due to exclusive reliance on high-efficiency boilers. However, electricity costs are five times higher than in the reference case. This is because all electricity must be purchased from the grid, with no on-site generation or revenue from electricity sales.

Conversely, Scenario 7, where the CHP operates at full load continuously, results in higher gas consumption. Yet, despite having the same level of electricity purchases from the grid as electrical-load-following scenarios, its electricity costs are significantly lower, and even negative, due to maximized electricity sales to the grid, generating revenues that offset and surpass the purchasing costs.

When considering Primary Energy Savings (PES), thermal-load-following scenarios outperform the reference case thanks to reduced use of the diverter, minimizing thermal energy waste and improving overall CHP efficiency. Electrical-load-following scenarios achieve PES values comparable to the reference case. As expected, Scenario 6 yields no primary energy savings due to the absence of cogeneration while Scenario 7, despite high CHP usage, shows slightly lower PES than the reference case due to increased thermal energy rejection. Nevertheless, PES remains above the 10% threshold in all cases, except for Scenario 6.

TEE (White Certificates) revenues are highest in electrical-load-following scenarios and in Scenario 7. This is because TEE incentives are linked to RISP, an absolute value based on energy production, rather than PES. The greater the energy output, the higher the RISP and the corresponding incentives.

Taking all factors into account, Scenarios 1, 2, and 3 sustain higher total operating costs than the reference case, despite achieving the lowest gas consumption. This is mainly due to the higher PUN (electricity price) relative to PSV (natural gas price), which causes the increased electricity expenses to outweigh the savings from reduced natural gas use. In contrast, Scenarios 4, 5, and 7 result in lower operating costs and, in some cases, additional revenues from electricity sales or incentives.

2.4.2. CHP optimal manamegement strategy

This section introduces the CHP optimal manamegement strategy, developed based on the heuristic scenarios outlined in the previous section. The model aims to minimize total operating costs while ensuring that the global PES remains above the regulatory threshold required for eligibility to TEE incentives. This approach ensures that the cogeneration system continues to meet High-Efficiency Cogeneration (CAR) standards while maximizing economic performance.

The optimization relies on an hourly comparison of the first five heuristic scenarios, applying the following selection criteria:

Scenarios in which the hourly PES falls below a predefined threshold ($PES_{\text{threshold}}$) are excluded. The $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ is arbitrarily chosen to ensure that the global PES consistently exceeds the CAR compliance threshold, thereby guaranteeing continued access to TEE incentives. Among the remaining eligible scenarios, the one with the lowest hourly operating cost is selected.

If no scenario meets the $PES_{\text{threshold}}$, Scenario 6 is selected by default. In this case, the CHP unit is deactivated, and all thermal and electrical demands are met through the boiler system and grid electricity, respectively. This case will be referred as Case 1.

For this analysis, it is assumed that TEEs are calculated and issued on an hourly basis, and that even fractional certificates contribute to revenue generation. The reference efficiencies used for calculating PES and RISP are held constant and are aligned with the average values derived from the annual results.

Since the optimization is based on hourly data, the average power used to calculate TEEs is considered equivalent to the hourly electrical energy output. To avoid overestimating the system performance, PES is calculated by accounting for the entire electricity production and fuel input, excluding any contribution from the virtual machine.

Although the number of TEEs generated may differ slightly from the annual estimation, these assumptions are acceptable, as the variation has a negligible impact on the total operating cost.

2.4.2.1. Possibility to sell electricity to the grid

The previous case considers only electricity self consumption. This additional scenario follows the same optimization methodology but extends the scenario pool to include Scenario 7, in addition to the first five heuristic scenarios. This case will be referred as Case 2.

The purpose of this case is to assess how results would change if POLIMI Energy Commission is more inclined to sell electricity to the grid, accepting the operational trade-offs of running the CHP system at full load continuously, such as increased wear and maintenance requirements.

By incorporating Scenario 7, the model explores the economic potential of maximizing electricity export revenues, while still applying the same selection logic regarding PES compliance and cost minimization.

2.4.2.1. Results post-processing

In the operation of the CHP unit, maintaining continuity is essential. Frequent start-stop cycles can cause several issues, including grid instability, increased maintenance needs, and undesirable transient behavior during system startup. To address these concerns, the optimization model incorporates an additional operational constraint: a minimum on/off duration of two hours. Specifically, once the CHP unit is shut down, it must remain off for at least two hours before it can restart. Conversely, once activated, it must stay in operation for a minimum of two hours.

Figure 19. Comparison of the CHP operation in the raw optimized results and after the post-processing.

The inclusion of this constraint results in a modest increase in CHP operating hours, and therefore a slight rise in total gas consumption. Since the modified dispatch is not strictly optimal, the total operating cost also increases marginally. Nevertheless, as visible from [Figure](#)

~~19Figure 19~~, the impact is minimal: the overall deviation in results remains within approximately 0.2%, confirming that system performance is not significantly affected.

2.4.2.2. Effect of $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ on optimization results

~~Figure 20~~**Figure 20** illustrates the variation in global PES and total cost reduction as a function of the PES threshold $PES_{\text{threshold}}$. Results are shown for both optimization cases: the self-consumption case and the electricity-sales case.

In both cases, the global PES remains largely unaffected by changes in $PES_{\text{threshold}}$, consistently staying above the CAR compliance limit, even for very low threshold values. This indicates that the optimal combination of scenarios naturally ensures compliance with TEE eligibility requirements, without the need to impose strict hourly PES constraints.

Maximum cost savings are achieved when no PES constraint is applied (i.e., $PES_{\text{threshold}} < -30\%$). Imposing a stricter PES threshold limits CHP operation and triggers the use of Scenario 6, which relies entirely on the boiler and grid electricity and is significantly more expensive. Therefore, no $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ constraint is applied in the final optimized model.

Figure 20. Global PES and total operating cost reduction as a function of PES threshold

2.4.3. Yearly Optimal Control Mode Distribution

Table 3.1 shows the yearly distribution of CHP operating hours across different scenarios in the optimized model for both cases. It also includes a separate category for hours in which the CHP operates simultaneously at full capacity for both thermal and electrical demand—outside standard load-following modes. The same data reported in Table 4 are visually represented in ~~Figure 21~~**Figure 24**, where it is possible to understand the distribution of the different scenarios over the year.

In the electricity-sale case (case 2), 88% of CHP operating hours occur at maximum load (Scenario 7), highlighting the economic advantage of maximizing electricity exports. Thermal-

and electrical-load-following modes are selected only when the Zonal Price does not justify the additional gas consumption associated with full-load operation.

Table 4. Operating hours distribution for the self-consumption and electricity-sale cases

Scenario Type	Scenario	Case 1: Self-consumption	Case 2: Electricity sale
Thermal-load-following	S1	1424	238
	S2	145	103
	S3	45	45
Electrical-load-following	S4	6523	74
	S5	0	0
Nominal condition		623	623
No CHP	S6	0	0
CHP at max load	S7	0	7677

■ T-L-following ■ E-L-following ■ Nominal

■ T-L-following ■ E-L-following ■ Nominal ■ Max Load

Figure 21. Optimal CHP control mode distribution along the year for Case 1 (top) and Case 2 (bottom)

In the self-consumption case (case 1), the hours that would have been assigned to maximum-load operation are redistributed, with a clear preference for electrical-load-following (74% of operating hours), due to the higher cost of electricity relative to natural gas. Hours at nominal conditions remain unchanged in both cases, as they correspond to simultaneous high thermal and electrical demand. Thermal-load-following hours in the self-consumption case are concentrated during nighttime in the cold season, when low electricity prices make grid purchasing more economical. In the electricity-sales case, thermal-load-following appears primarily during daylight hours in midseason, when the PUN/PSV ratio is too low to justify CHP operation.

2.4.4. Results of optimal control strategy

Table 5 compares the global performance of the optimized model against the reference results for both cases considered. The results highlight that:

- Operating cost reduction of 13% in the self-consumption case and 22% in the electricity-sales case can be obtained.
- In the electricity-sales case, electricity costs become negative, meaning revenues from sales exceed grid purchase costs.
- TEE revenues increase in both cases due to higher RISP values, a result of the greater useful energy production.
- Scope 1 emissions increase in both cases due to longer CHP operation and higher natural gas usage, which offsets reductions in Scope 2 and 3 emissions.
- Despite the overall cost optimization, the PES efficiency decreases, particularly in the electricity-sales case (10% vs. 13% in self-consumption), as maximum-load operation sacrifices fuel efficiency.

To account for the trade-off between emissions and cost, a fictitious carbon tax is introduced on direct (Scope 1) emissions. The composition of illustrations in [Figure 22](#) presents how increasing this tax shifts the optimal control strategy: maximum-load operation decreases, while thermal- and electrical-load-following increase. The first hours to transition are midseason periods with lower PZ. Only winter morning and evening peaks consistently justify maximum-load operation even under high carbon taxes.

Figure 22. Optimal CHP control mode distribution along the year for different carbon taxes (60, 90, 120, 175 €/ton)

Table 5. Overall results comparison between optimized model and the reference case - self-consumption (Case 1) vs electricity-sale (Case 2)

Parameter	Reference	Case 1	Var%	Case 2	Var%
$m_{NG,CHP}$	2,800	3,201	14%	4,061	45%
$m_{NG,CD}$	497	339	-32%	334	-33%
$m_{NG,TOT}$	3,298	3,540	7%	4,395	33%
CHP operating hours	7,056	8,292	18%	8,491	20%
Boiler operating hours	2,462	1,755	-29%	1,446	-41%
Electrical Energy CHP	11,292	12,893	14%	16,814	49%
Thermal Energy CHP	6,446	7,957	23%	8,004	24%
Energy from fuel CHP	26,605	30,413	14%	38,576	45%
Energy to the grid	877	416	-53%	4,152	373%
Energy from the grid	3,630	1,567	-57%	1,382	-62%
PES	18.40%	18.32%	-	18.64%	-
RISP	7,349	8,928	21%	9,529	30%
Number of TEE	875	1,051	20%	1,119	28%
Cost of Natural Gas	1,457,037	1,541,853	6%	1,898,058	30%
Cost of Electricity	349,368	108,041	-69%	-381,615	-209%
TEE revenues	218,557	262,664	20%	279,724	28%
Total operating cost	1,587,747	1,387,230	-13%	1,236,719	-22%
Scope 1 emissions	6,450	6,925	7%	8,596	33%
Scope 2 emissions	910	393	-57%	346	-62%
Scope 3 emissions	-220	-104	53%	-1,041	-373%
Total emissions	7,140	7,213	1%	7,902	11%

2.4.4.1. Typical Week Analysis

Figure 23 to Figure 26 present reference weeks for cold and hot periods, comparing both optimization strategies.

- In **self-consumption mode** (Figure 23 and Figure 24), the control strategy closely resembles the reference case, suggesting that similar logic may already be in place at the plant, even if influenced by operational uncertainties which cannot be captured in historical data.
- In **electricity-sales mode** (Figure 25 and Figure 26), the system maximizes both electricity exports and waste heat generation. While this strategy increases fuel use, the excess thermal energy can partially displace boiler operation, especially during the hot season, when waste heat is abundant.

However, during the cold season, most of the waste heat is generated at night or weekends and can only replace the boiler for brief periods. This motivates the analysis in Section 3, which investigates the potential of RESTORE seasonal thermal energy storage to shift excess summer heat to winter demand.

Figure 23. Reference week cold period - Optimized Model (electricity-sale)

Figure 24. Reference week hot period - Optimized Model (electricity-sale)

Figure 25. Reference week cold period - Optimized Model (self-consumption)

Figure 26. Reference week hot period - Optimized Model (self-consumption)

2.4.5. Optimization of PV-integrated system operation

2.4.5.1. PV system integration

In 2023, 11 photovoltaic (PV) plants were installed on buildings rooftops, reaching a total peak power of approximately 1 MW. In 2024, 3 additional PV plants were added, increasing the nominal power to 1.5 MW.

From the results proposed above, it results evident that the optimization push to maximize the revenues generated by selling energy to the grid, it increases the gas consumption in both self-consumption and electricity-sales cases.

The integration of renewable energy sources, such as photovoltaic (PV) systems, can partially offset this effect by covering a share of the electrical demand. However, due to the inherent variability of PV generation, highly dependent on weather conditions, its output must be given dispatching priority. Consequently, the CHP unit should be operated in a coordinated manner, adapting its schedule to complement the intermittent PV production.

Photovoltaic (PV) power plants are incorporated into all seven heuristic scenarios, leading to new optimized results. To ensure meaningful results, and considering that the installed PV capacity remained nearly constant between 2023 and 2024, the system is assumed to include a PV plant with a peak power of 1.5 MW.

The hourly PV yield is estimated using online simulation tools based on historical weather data. While these platforms provide a convenient means of generating typical PV production profiles, it is important to acknowledge their limitations in accuracy. More reliable simulations would require specialized software (e.g., PVSyst), which allows for detailed system modeling and

site-specific adjustments. However, since PV production is not the primary focus of this analysis, a simplified approach is adopted. The hourly solar energy yield is simulated using Renewables.ninja, with the input parameters provided in Table 6.

The weekly PV energy yield throughout the year is illustrated in [Figure 27](#).

Table 6. Solar PV plant assumptions and parameters

Parameter	Value
Latitude	45.4810
Longitude	9.2326
Dataset	MERRA-2 (global)
Capacity	1500 kW
System loss (fraction)	0.1
Tracking	Not present
Tilt angle	35°
Azimuth angle	180°

Figure 27. Weekly PV electricity production for 2023.

2.4.5.1. CHP operating strategy modifications

The integration of PV plants requires a revision of CHP control strategies across all previously defined scenarios:

- Scenarios S1–S3 (thermal-load-following): The CHP operates based on thermal demand, without adapting to PV output. CHP and PV electricity are combined to meet electrical demand. Any surplus is exported to the grid; deficits are covered by grid purchases.
- Scenarios S4–S5 (electrical-load-following): PV generation takes priority. The CHP adjusts its output to meet the remaining electrical demand. Excess electricity is exported; deficits are covered by the grid.

- Scenario 6: PV generation simply reduces grid electricity purchases, without affecting CHP operation.
- Scenario 7: The CHP operates continuously at full load, regardless of PV production. PV electricity is exported if surplus or used to reduce grid imports during high demand.

2.4.6. PV-integrated results and optimal control distribution

Table 7 summarizes the annual results of integrating a 1.5 MW PV plant into the internal grid. Both self-consumption and electricity-sales cases are evaluated and compared to the optimal results without PV integration.

Overall, most performance indicators remain largely unchanged. As expected, PV generation reduces electricity purchases from the grid while increasing the amount of electricity exported. This additional energy production is the main contributor to the observed reduction in total operating costs.

In the self-consumption case, the integration of PV results in a slight reduction in CHP natural gas consumption and associated cost. This is due to the decrease in the residual electrical demand, which occasionally drops below the CHP unit's minimum load threshold. During such hours, the CHP cannot operate in electrical-load-following mode and switches to thermal-load-following mode instead, running at minimum load to satisfy thermal demand and exporting excess electricity. As this condition recurs throughout the year, overall gas consumption decreases. Additionally, the number of hours during which the CHP operates at maximum load to meet high thermal and electrical demand also decrease, due to the lower overall electricity demand.

In the electricity-sales case, PV integration affects only the electricity exchanged with the grid, with all other variables remaining consistent with the original optimization. As shown in [Figure 28](#) the control strategy remains unchanged since the system is already maximizing grid exports, so further increases in electricity production do not modify the CHP operation.

As expected, a decrease in total emissions is also observed compared to the case where no PV-integration is considered. In the self-consumption case, emissions fall even below those of the reference case, and this improvement is primarily attributed to reductions in both natural gas consumption and electricity imports from the grid.

Similarly, in the electricity-sales case, total emissions are significantly reduced from 11% down to just 3%. While direct emissions from the CHP unit remain unchanged compared to the no-PV integration case, the notable drop in grid electricity purchases, combined with increased electricity exports, brings total emissions close to the levels observed in the reference scenario.

Table 7. Overall results comparison between optimized model with and without the PV integration and the reference case - self-consumption (Case 1) vs electricity-sale (Case 2).

Parameter	Reference	Optimized Case 1	Var%	PV 1500 Case 1	Var%	Optimized Case 2	Var%	PV 1500 Case 2	Var%
m _{NG,CHP}	2,800	3,201	14%	3,003	7%	4,061	45%	4,024	44%
m _{NG,CD}	497	339	-32%	340	-32%	334	-33%	334	-33%
m _{NG,TOT}	3,298	3,540	7%	3,343	1%	4,395	33%	4,357	32%
CHP operating hours	7,056	8,292	18%	8,129	15%	8,491	20%	8,493	20%
Boiler operating hours	2,462	1,755	-29%	1,903	-23%	1,446	-41%	1,447	-41%
Electrical Energy CHP	11,292	12,893	14%	12,010	6%	16,814	49%	16,648	47%
Thermal Energy CHP	6,446	7,957	23%	7,948	23%	8,004	24%	8,005	24%
Energy from fuel CHP	26,605	30,413	14%	28,532	7%	38,576	45%	38,224	44%
Energy to the grid	877	416	-53%	812	-7%	4,152	373%	5,212	494%
Energy from the grid	3,630	1,567	-57%	746	-79%	1,382	-62%	508	-86%
PES	18.40%	18.32%	-	18.08%	-	18.64%	-	18.49%	-
RISP	7,349	8,928	21%	8,814	20%	9,529	30%	9,526	29%
Number of TEE	875	1,051	20%	1,046	18%	1,119	28%	1,128	28%
Cost of Natural Gas	1,457,037	1,541,853	6%	1,466,938	1%	1,898,058	30%	1,886,121	29%
Cost of Electricity	349,368	108,041	-69%	-32,301	-109%	-381,615	-209%	-605,823	-273%
TEE revenues	218,657	262,664	20%	261,511	18%	279,724	28%	281,955	28%
Total operating cost	1,587,747	1,387,230	-13%	1,173,126	-26%	1,236,719	-22%	998,343	-37%
Scope 1 Emissions	6,450	6,925	7%	6,540	1%	8,596	33%	8,523	32%
Scope 2 Emissions	911	393	-57%	187	-79%	347	-62%	127	-86%
Scope 3 Emissions	-220	-104	53%	-204	7%	-1,042	-373%	-1,308	-494%
Total Emissions	7,140	7,213	1%	6,523	-9%	7,902	11%	7,342	3%

Figure 28. Optimal CHP control mode distribution considering PV integration for self-consumption (Case 1, top) vs electricity-sale (Case 2, bottom).

The integration of a PV system reduces the plant’s electrical demand during peak hours, especially in the hot season, when PV yield is highest. However, the operation of the CHP unit remains largely unaffected, following the same control strategy as in the reference configuration. In practice, the electricity generated by the PV system primarily offsets grid purchases but rarely impacts CHP operation. As a result, although the current PV capacity significantly lowers operational costs, it does not lead to a meaningful change in the CHP unit’s behavior.

3. RESTORE TCES Integration

Even though the optimized control strategy has significantly reduced total operating costs, more than half of the recoverable thermal energy is still wasted, primarily due to the low thermal demand during many periods of the year. For example, in the PV-integrated results under the electricity-sales scenario, the total recoverable thermal energy amounts to 18.36 GWh annually, yet only 8 GWh are effectively utilized, meaning that approximately 56% is discarded, mostly via the CHP diverter.

To address this inefficiency, the most effective solution is the integration of the RESTORE ThermoChemical Energy Storage (TCES) system, capable of recovering and storing excess thermal energy otherwise lost to the environment. In contrast, the use of a electricity-only storage, as for example a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), to store excess electricity is not recommended for two main reasons:

- The amount of excess thermal energy (10.4 GWh) is nearly three times higher than the excess electricity exported to the grid (5.4 GWh).
- Electricity sales to the grid play a key role in reducing total operating costs. Diverting this electricity to storage would eliminate associated revenues, ultimately increasing total costs.

The primary objective of TCES integration is therefore to reduce natural gas consumption, particularly by offsetting boiler usage, without compromising the cost reductions achieved through optimized CHP dispatch.

However, because the TCES is charged with heat recovered from the CHP, any strategy that reduces CHP operating hours could also decrease the amount of heat available for storage, potentially resulting in unintended negative impacts. As such, the initial goal is to reduce boiler gas consumption, which currently accounts for just 8% of total gas usage, by supplying its thermal load from the TCES stored heat. Nevertheless, to realize a meaningful reduction in total gas consumption, it will be necessary to develop additional strategies to limit CHP operation while maintaining economic performance.

As already discussed, thermal energy waste is primarily concentrated during the hot period, when demand is lowest. Conversely, in the cold period, thermal demand often exceeds the CHP capacity, requiring boiler support. This seasonal mismatch between excess heat generation and peak demand supports the case for a seasonal thermal energy storage system, capable of shifting unused heat from the summer to the winter.

3.1. User Case definition

3.1.1. Preliminary analysis of seasonal TCES integration

As a preliminary study, a simplified model of the RESTORE technology is used to assess the feasibility of the integration of a seasonal storage, varying storage capacity to assess the impact on total operating cost and gas consumption.

3.1.1.1. Modelling Assumptions

According to the results obtained by TU-WIEN in the framework of the RESTORE project, copper sulfate (CuSO_4) has been selected for the TCES reaction. The storage charging temperature is assumed equal to 130°C , thus lower than the exhaust gas temperature ($>300^\circ\text{C}$), but sufficient for heat recovery after partial cooling to $\sim 100^\circ\text{C}$. On the other hand, the storage discharging temperature is lower than the charging one, and equal to 125°C , because of the endothermic and exothermic nature of the underlying chemical reactions.

It is important to note that the TCES system exhibits an inherent inefficiency due to the need to heat water up to its boiling point in order to produce steam for the hydration reaction. This thermal input does not directly contribute to energy storage, but is necessary to enable the reactivation of the thermochemical material. For this reason, an additional conversion factor, estimated at around 72.5% is considered to model this process.

Given these temperatures and based on the following performance coefficients are assumed:

- Heat pump COP: 5.5
- TCES thermal efficiency: 0.725
- Heat engine efficiency: 0.1
- Round-trip efficiency: 0.4

Figure 29. Heat pump and heat engine (ORC) power flows.

While COP and efficiency depend on machine size and off-design operation, for sake of simplicity and to reduce the preliminary model computational time, constant values are assumed. Moreover, since no specific design or commercial model of the heat pump and ORC is considered, no constraints are imposed on the charging or discharging power.

Given the heuristic approach adopted, the seasonal TCES integration model relies on predefined hourly CHP operation data to identify available surplus heat. Consequently, the CHP dispatch from the electricity-sales scenario is used as a fixed input. As a result, the storage system cannot influence CHP scheduling, making this strategy inherently suboptimal.

Starting from the PV-integrated optimized model results presented in Section 2.4.6, four TCES control modes are defined for each hour:

- **TCES Charging (Mode 1)**

When CHP produces more heat than needed, the surplus is stored instead of being discarded. The stored heat is:

$$Q_{th,HT} = Q_{th,LT} + W_{el,IN} = Q_{th,LT} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{COP_{HP} - 1}\right)$$

where $Q_{th,HT}$ is the heat stored in the tank, and $Q_{th,LT}$ is the heat otherwise wasted by the CHP. It is important to highlight that, in the RISP and TEE calculations, the heat stored is also considered as useful energy, as it is no longer wasted to the environment. If the storage is already full, mode 0 is applied.

- **TCES Discharging to Cover Boiler Demand (Mode -1)**

When demand exceeds CHP output and TCES State of Charge (SoC) is sufficient, the boiler is turned off, and its expected load is met by TCES. The heat extracted is:

$$Q_{th,HT} = Q_{th,boiler} + W_{el,OUT} = Q_{th,boiler} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\eta_{HE}}{\eta_{HE} - 1}\right)$$

- **TCES Discharging to Cover Total Demand (Mode -2)**

Used in the hot period to prevent prolonged storage saturation. Both CHP and boiler are shut off. Total thermal demand is met via TCES:

$$Q_{th,HT} = D_{th} + W_{el,OUT} = D_{th} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\eta_{HE}}{\eta_{HE} - 1}\right)$$

Where D_{th} is the total thermal demand.

This is only activated when CHP operates below a predefined $PES_{threshold}$, and TCES SoC is sufficient. A higher $PES_{threshold}$ leads to more frequent use of this mode, affecting both costs and natural gas usage.

- **Standby (No Charge/Discharge) (Mode 0)**

The TCES SoC remains unchanged.

To ensure annual consistency, the initial and final TCES SoC are aligned, with adjustments made according to storage capacity.

3.1.1.2. Results of seasonal TCES integration

Applying the outlined assumptions to the previous model, a multi-variable sensitivity analysis is conducted by varying both the storage capacity (250, 500, 1000, 2000, and 3000 MWh) and the $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ (-20%, -10%, 0%, +10%, +20%). Results, shown in [Figure 30](#), are expressed as percentage variations relative to the PV-integrated optimal results.

As storage capacity increases, total operating costs decrease, mainly due to reduced boiler usage. Since CHP operating hours remain unchanged, this also affects the energy exchanged with the grid. Notably, a 2000 MWh storage capacity is sufficient to eliminate boiler operation entirely. Correspondingly, total emissions decline, closely following the reduction in overall natural gas consumption, thus mainly driven by direct (Scope 1) emissions.

TOTAL OPERATING COST VARIATION

	250MWh	500MWh	1000MWh	2000MWh	3000MWh
-20%	-11.8%	-14.3%	-17.5%	-19.9%	-19.9%
-10%	-4.2%	-6.7%	-9.9%	-12.3%	-12.3%
0%	0.7%	-1.8%	-5.1%	-7.5%	-7.5%
10%	9.9%	9.9%	9.6%	4.6%	4.6%
20%	9.3%	8.8%	11.6%	10.1%	10.0%

TOTAL GAS CONSUMPTION VARIATION

	250MWh	500MWh	1000MWh	2000MWh	3000MWh
-20%	-4.7%	-5.7%	-6.3%	-7.6%	-7.6%
-10%	-15.7%	-16.7%	-17.8%	-18.6%	-18.6%
0%	-23.6%	-24.6%	-25.7%	-26.5%	-26.5%
10%	-35.9%	-38.8%	-40.9%	-42.5%	-42.5%
20%	-35.1%	-37.3%	-39.9%	-47.3%	-47.9%

TOTAL EMISSIONS

	250MWh	500MWh	1000MWh	2000MWh	3000MWh
-20%	-4.3%	-5.3%	-5.2%	-7.1%	-7.0%
-10%	-10.6%	-11.6%	-12.6%	-13.4%	-13.4%
0%	-15.1%	-16.0%	-17.1%	-17.8%	-17.8%
10%	-21.6%	-23.6%	-26.2%	-26.9%	-26.9%
20%	-21.0%	-22.5%	-24.0%	-29.7%	-29.7%

TOTAL CHP OPERATING HOURS

	250MWh	500MWh	1000MWh	2000MWh	3000MWh
-20%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
-10%	-11.9%	-11.9%	-11.9%	-11.9%	-11.9%
0%	-20.4%	-20.4%	-20.4%	-20.4%	-20.4%
10%	-33.7%	-36.1%	-37.7%	-37.7%	-37.7%
20%	-32.8%	-34.5%	-37.3%	-43.6%	-43.6%

TOTAL BOILERS OPERATING HOURS

	250MWh	500MWh	1000MWh	2000MWh	3000MWh
-20%	-72.0%	-82.3%	-91.8%	-100.0%	-100.0%
-10%	-72.0%	-82.3%	-91.8%	-100.0%	-100.0%
0%	-72.0%	-82.3%	-91.8%	-100.0%	-100.0%
10%	-70.8%	-77.3%	-84.6%	-100.0%	-100.0%
20%	-70.5%	-76.9%	-76.3%	-93.7%	-98.0%

Figure 30. Results of seasonal TCES integration as a function of TCES size (columns) and $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ (rows), reported as percentage with respect to the PV-integrated optimal results.

As $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ increases, CHP operating hours drop significantly. This leads to higher grid electricity purchases and reduced exports, which increases total costs. However, fewer CHP hours translate to lower gas consumption and reduced emissions. Yet, in the 10%–20% $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ range, emissions temporarily increase because Scope 2 and 3 emissions (from grid electricity) rise faster than the reduction in Scope 1 emissions, slowing the overall decline in emissions.

Table 8. Key parameters for different TCES capacities with $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ values for which total operating costs remain unchanged from the PV-integration results.

Max capacity [MWh]	PES threshold	Total cost	Total gas	Total emissions	CHP hours	Boiler hours
250	-1%	0%	-23%	-15%	-19%	-72%
500	2%	0%	-28%	-18%	-24%	-83%
1000	5%	0%	-32%	-21%	-28%	-92%
2000	7%	0%	-38%	-24%	-33%	-100%
3000	7%	0%	-38%	-24%	-33%	-100%

Table 8 reports the $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ values for which total operating costs remain unchanged from the PV-integration results, along with the associated changes in emissions and CHP operating hours. In all cases, emissions are reduced without compromising the cost savings achieved in previous models. As storage capacity grows, more CHP hours can be eliminated while still meeting thermal demand, because stored heat offsets boiler use. The increase in electricity costs is balanced by lower gas consumption from both CHP and boiler systems. Notably, beyond 2000 MWh, no additional benefits are observed, as the key performance indicators and parameters are the same.

Figure 31 shows the yearly storage trends for different capacities at 0% cost variation (see Table 8). Systems with 250-1000 MWh of TCES size are fully discharged early in the year and then switch to daily cycling until sufficient excess heat becomes available in March.

In contrast, the 2000 MWh system never reaches zero, with about 750 MWh remaining unused, indicating an oversizing of the TCES. A capacity between 1000 and 2000 MWh proves more effective, with 1400 MWh identified as optimal as it avoids daily cycling and it ensures full seasonal utilization without excessive leftover energy.

However, achieving a 30% further reduction in boiler demand (from -72% to -100%) requires a significant increase in storage, passing from 250 MWh to 1400 MWh (equal to +600%), entailing very large TCES volumes. For reference, assuming 2.07 GJ/m^3 for the energy density of a TCES based on copper sulfate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and considering a 30% in mass of a mixture of mineral and silicone oil to reduce costs and still have good cycle stability and foam mitigation, the overall storage tank volume would be equal to roughly 4350 m^3 , close to the volume of two Olympic swimming pools. Furthermore, considering a copper sulfate cost of 12€/kg and an average oil cost of 5.5 €/kg, the overall cost of just the storage material would be equal to around 75 M€.

It must be noted that this are optimistic estimates as they consider the possibility to store the steam required for the discharging process on the seasonal basis, which is actually not feasible. More conservative estimates would entail an energy density closer to 0.46 GJ/m^3 and thus volumes around eight Olympic swimming pools, with cost higher than 340 M€.

On the other hand, the volume and cost of the daily storage solution are significantly smaller. A 10 MWh TCES would require a total volume of approximately 31 m³ - comparable to a small shipping container - and an estimated cost of around half a million euros.

Thus, while seasonal TCES integration can significantly reduce emissions and costs, its feasibility is limited by space and capital cost requirements. Consequently, the next section focuses on smaller-scale storage systems suitable for daily cycling.

Figure 31. Trend of the TCES SoC for different capacities.

3.1.2. Preliminary analysis of daily TCES integration

Small storage capacities in the range of 10–50 MWh are significantly more feasible from both technical and practical perspectives compared to large-scale systems. However, with limited capacity, seasonal storage is no longer practical; instead, the system must rely on diurnal or at maximum weekly thermal storage.

This shift fundamentally alters the CHP and boilers control strategy. While seasonal storage allows excess heat from the hot season to be stored and used during the cold season to eliminate boiler demand, short-term storage operates on a much smaller timescale. In this case, waste heat is stored during low-demand periods, so primarily at nighttime, and used to support the boilers during peak hours. This approach inherently limits the reduction in boiler operating hours, as peak thermal demand typically occurs in the cold season, whereas recoverable waste heat is more abundant in the hot season.

The same analysis as presented in Section 3.1.1 is extended to storage capacities of 10 MWh, 25 MWh, and 50 MWh. Even without reducing the operating hours of the CHP unit, minor emissions reductions can be achieved by decreasing boiler usage. For example, with a 50 MWh storage capacity, over 60% of the dependence on boiler operation can be eliminated. This confirms that simply shifting excess heat from nighttime to peak daytime hours is not sufficient to eliminate the need for boiler operation.

Furthermore, the impact on total emissions remains limited, as boiler natural gas consumption constitutes only a small fraction of the overall natural gas use and a significant reduction in emissions can only be achieved by curtailing CHP operating hours.

TOTAL OPERATING COST VARIATION

	10	25	50
-20%	-5.1%	-7.7%	-8.7%
-10%	2.4%	-0.1%	-1.1%
0%	6.7%	4.4%	3.7%
10%	13.4%	11.7%	11.1%
20%	14.8%	12.2%	11.3%

TOTAL GAS CONSUMPTION VARIATION

	10	25	50
-20%	-2.4%	-3.3%	-3.7%
-10%	-13.4%	-14.4%	-14.7%
0%	-20.7%	-22.0%	-22.6%
10%	-29.9%	-31.8%	-32.7%
20%	-31.3%	-32.2%	-32.7%

TOTAL EMISSIONS VARIATION

	10	25	50
-20%	-2.1%	-3.0%	-3.4%
-10%	-8.4%	-9.4%	-9.7%
0%	-12.4%	-13.6%	-14.1%
10%	-17.0%	-18.6%	-19.2%
20%	-17.8%	-18.7%	-19.2%

TOTAL CHP OPERATING HOURS

	10	25	50
-20%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
-10%	-11.9%	-11.9%	-11.9%
0%	-19.7%	-20.0%	-20.4%
10%	-29.6%	-30.8%	-31.3%
20%	-31.1%	-31.2%	-31.3%

TOTAL BOILERS OPERATING HOURS

	10	25	50
-20%	-49.3%	-60.1%	-63.2%
-10%	-49.4%	-60.1%	-63.2%
0%	-49.1%	-60.1%	-63.2%
10%	-46.8%	-57.6%	-60.8%
20%	-46.7%	-57.4%	-60.6%

Figure 32. Results of daily TCES integration as a function of TCES size (columns, in MWh) and $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ (rows), reported as percentage with respect to the PV-integrated optimal results.

As shown in Table 9, the same total operating cost as in the PV-integrated results can be maintained even with a relatively modest reduction in CHP operating hours (around -10%), although this leads to a proportionally smaller decrease in emissions (approximately -8%). Therefore, the only viable pathway to substantial emissions reduction involves accepting a reduction in the total operating cost savings gained through the optimized CHP control.

Table 9. Key parameters for different TCES daily storage capacities with $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ values for which total operating costs remain unchanged from the PV-integration results.

Max capacity [MWh]	PES threshold	Total cost	Total gas	Total emissions	CHP hours	Boiler hours
10	-12%	0.9%	-12.1%	-7.7%	-10.4%	-49.0%
25	-10%	-0.1%	-14.4%	-9.4%	-11.9%	-60.0%
50	-6%	0.2%	-16.6%	-10.7%	-13.9%	-63.0%

~~Figure 33~~ **Figure 33** illustrates the variation in total operating costs and emissions as CHP operating hours are reduced (i.e., as the $PES_{\text{threshold}}$ increases). The green-shaded regions highlight the admissible range of operation for each storage capacity, where neither the cost savings nor the emissions reductions achieved in earlier models are compromised.

Specifically, total operating cost variations are with respect to the PV-integrated model results, as the objective is to maintain the improvements previously obtained through the CHP management strategy optimization. Conversely, emissions are referenced to the reference model results, thus being more conservative.

As storage capacity increases, this admissible range broadens. Medium-sized storage systems, more specifically those with capacities of 250 MWh and 500 MWh, offer the most balanced solution. These capacities are not only technically and spatially feasible, but also enable further reductions in either operating costs or emissions without worsening the other.

In the context of this case study, diurnal storage systems can be implemented relatively easily, as the Leonardo campus is surrounded by adjacent buildings that could potentially host the required infrastructure. However, in this configuration, achieving substantial emissions reductions would necessarily involve a compromise in cost savings.

In contrast, large-scale seasonal storage offers the best performance in terms of both emissions and cost reduction, with decreases of up to 37% in total operating costs and 20% in emissions compared to the Benchmark Model. Nevertheless, due to the enormous volume required, this solution remains unfeasible for the location of this case study.

Based on the conclusions outlined above, particularly the limited feasibility of seasonal storage due to space constraints and the excessive capacity and cost required to fully displace boiler operation, **the subsequent analysis focuses on diurnal storage solutions**, which offer a more practical balance between performance and implementation.

Figure 33. Results of daily TCES integration as a function of TCES size (columns, in MWh) and $PES_{threshold}$ (rows), reported as percentage with respect to the PV-integrated optimal results.

3.1. Representing Use-Case VI in the IPSE GO Platform

To align with all other RESTORE Use-Cases' virtual models, Use-Case VI has also been simulated within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, powered by the IPSE GO Platform, which is a web-based simulation and optimization environment designed to support the virtual implementation of complex energy systems. Within the RESTORE project, IPSE GO plays a central role in the digital representation and testing of six real-world use-cases, each reflecting distinct district heating and cooling (DHC) configurations. The platform allows users to model, simulate, and optimize integrated energy systems combining components such as thermochemical storage, renewable heat sources, and thermodynamic cycles.

One of the core strengths of IPSE GO lies in its flexibility and modular design. It supports the integration of a wide variety of components and subsystems, enabling partners to replicate specific operational settings and boundary conditions from each use-case. For each virtual scenario, the platform facilitates the configuration of heat sources, sinks, storage units, and control strategies, ensuring that the simulation mirrors the physical dynamics of the real installation as accurately as possible.

In addition to basic system modelling, IPSE GO incorporates advanced optimization tools that help evaluate the system's performance under different operational parameters. Users can simulate dynamic behavior over time, analyze energy flows, and test alternative layouts or control algorithms. This supports the identification of the most effective technical solutions for each local context and ensures that the RESTORE concept is not only functional but also efficient and scalable.

The platform also plays a key role in promoting replicability and transparency across the project. Its cloud-based nature facilitates collaboration between project partners, enabling remote access, version tracking, and shared testing environments. By consolidating all use-cases in a unified digital workspace, IPSE GO enables systematic benchmarking, comparison, and validation of the RESTORE solution across diverse European settings.

3.2. Input Data

The results of the previous yearly simulations are now used to develop a comprehensive system-level model of the RESTORE configuration within the IPSE Go simulation platform. This model integrates all major subsystems - such as the HP unit, the thermochemical storage (TCES) components, the ORC and district heating exchangers - into a unified framework. Due to the observations proposed in Section 3.1.1.2, the focus is specifically on the daily storage configuration, which involves regular charging and discharging cycles within a 24-hour period.

By simulating the entire RESTORE system with the IPSE Go platform, the model enables a detailed assessment of performance metrics such as energy efficiency, thermal balancing, operational flexibility, and the potential contribution of TCES to decarbonization and cost reduction objectives.

3.2.1. Assumptions

The TCM charging process within the POLIMI TCES system is driven by the recovery of waste heat from the Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit operating on the POLIMI Leonardo campus. The CHP system, based on a Jenbacher JMS 612 GS-N.L. natural gas engine, produces both electricity and thermal energy. During operation, a significant amount of heat is released through engine cooling circuits and flue gases, typically reaching temperatures of around 300°C. A portion of this waste heat, which would be delivered to the district heating network or otherwise be released to the environment, is redirected to support the TCES charging process. For the purpose of this analysis, the design of the system is carried out considering the most critical operational scenario, in which the TCES unit must absorb the entire thermal power rejected by the CHP unit, which amounts to 1791 kW (see Table 1). This assumption ensures that the system is dimensioned to handle the maximum expected thermal input, particularly during periods when the district heating demand is minimal and no alternative sinks are available for the CHP's waste heat.

To integrate this heat source, the flue gases are first passed through an existing exhaust-to-water heat exchanger used in the cogeneration setup, which forms part of the intermediate loop. An additional heat exchanger and a dedicated hot water loop are used to extract a controlled amount of thermal energy and deliver it to the thermochemical storage loop. This integration allows the TCES system to capture and store surplus thermal energy during CHP operation periods, especially when the immediate DH demand is low or when daily storage flexibility is desired.

In the charging reactor, the thermochemical material (TCM), copper sulfate pentahydrate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), undergoes an endothermic dehydration reaction. The absorbed heat is used to break molecular bonds, removing water from the TCM and chemically storing the thermal energy. The reactor operates under tightly controlled temperature and pressure conditions and internal stirring mechanisms ensure uniform heat and mass transfer during the reaction.

Before entering the reactor, the discharged TCM is preheated using an auxiliary thermal oil loop to ensure it meets the required inlet conditions. After the dehydration reaction is completed, the charged TCM slurry is cooled down and pumped into dedicated storage vessels designed to maintain its stability and prevent premature hydration.

The discharging phase of the TCES system is activated when thermal (or electrical) energy is needed beyond what the CHP can provide instantaneously. In this mode, the charged TCM is

retrieved from storage and directed to a discharging reactor, where it reacts exothermically with injected steam to release the stored heat. This energy is then supplied to an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) module for cogeneration of electricity and thermal power to be delivered to the POLIMI Leonardo campus district heating network.

The ORC system includes an evaporator, a turbine, a condenser, and a recuperator to improve cycle efficiency. The working fluid selected is Novec649, coherently with the experimental campaign run at POLIMI laboratory on the reversible ORC/HP prototype provided by Enerbasque.

Once the hydration reaction is complete, the TCM, which is now completely hydrated ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), is pumped back to its original storage tanks, closing the cycle. The entire discharging configuration operates independently from the already installed CHP, allowing the TCES module to function as a flexible and dispatchable energy asset within the system.

3.3. IPSE GO Virtual Case implementation

This chapter defines the implementation performed in the IPSE GO platform for the User Case VI (UC6) model definition and design assumptions.

3.3.1. UC6 Model definition

The integration of the thermochemical energy storage model in the POLIMI Leonardo campus use-case VI into IPSE GO platform has been based on the design proposed in [2]. The thermochemical storage system is based on a continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which requires several dedicated subsystems to effectively perform the charging and discharging reactions. The main components, based on the experimental setup developed at TU Wien, are:

- The Salt Feed Tank (1), which stores the solid thermochemical material (e.g., $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or its dehydrated forms)
- The Mixer Unit (2), which combines solid salt with recirculated or fresh oil mixture to create a suspension prior to entering the reactor.
- The Oil Storage Tank (3), which supplies fresh oil used in the suspension mixture and thermal circulation.
- The Reactor Vessel (4) consisting of the main reaction zone where heat is supplied via an internal heat exchanger to drive the (de)hydration reactions. It includes:
 - Anchor and propeller stirrers for homogenous suspension mixing.
 - Optional nitrogen sparging system to reduce foaming during dehydration.
- The Heat Exchanger System (5 and 6), which provides or extracts heat during charging/discharging via thermal oil, ensuring the reactor maintains the desired operating temperature.
- The Condensation Unit and Water Tank (7), which captures water vapor released during dehydration.

- The Solid–Liquid Separation Unit (8–10), which uses suction filtration or sedimentation to separate reacted salt from oil. It includes:
 - Separator (filter mesh or settling tank)
 - Screw conveyor or rotary valve for salt removal
 - Recirculation loop for recovered oil
- The Salt Storage Tank (11), which receives the reacted (charged or discharged) salt for storage.
- The Control and Measurement Cabinet (12), which contains all electrical and control interfaces, including:
 - Oil flow meters, temperature sensors, and water dosing system.
 - Speed and direction control for conveyors and pumps.
 - Data acquisition system for thermal and chemical process monitoring.
- The Water Injection Pump (13, discharging only), which precisely injects stoichiometric water into the reactor for salt rehydration via a hollow stirrer shaft.

The design approach is modular and scalable for pilot and pre-commercial applications like RESTORE’s integration at the POLIMI Leonardo campus.

Figure 34. Charging TCES concept: equipment and subsystems

Figure 35. Discharging TCES concept: equipment and subsystems

3.3.2. The Charging Mode

~~Figure 36~~ ~~Figure 36~~ illustrates the complete configuration of the TCES system operating in charging mode, as implemented in the IPSE Go simulation platform for Use Case VI (POLIMI Leonardo campus). The process involves the endothermic dehydration of the thermochemical material (TCM), $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where the thermal energy from the flue gases of the CHP unit is used to charge the TCES by chemically extracting water.

On the left-hand side of the charging phase plant layout, the system receives a suspension of discharged TCM directly from the storage. This suspension is heated using a thermal oil mixture and converted into its dehydrated form (CuSO_4). Heat transfer is achieved through a heat exchanger coupled with a continuously stirred tank reactor. Following the reaction, the charged suspension is cooled down via an auxiliary thermal oil loop and subsequently sent to a dedicated storage unit.

The main TCES subcomponents, along with their input variables, are:

- **Auxiliary Thermal Oil Loop**, which consist of a closed-loop system responsible for pre-heating and post-cooling of the TCM suspension through dedicated heat exchangers. It transfers heat to the TCM before the dehydration reaction and removes residual heat after charging. The loop is equipped with a dedicated thermal oil pump. To reduce costs and still have good cycle stability and foam mitigation a mixture of mineral and silicone oil has been selected.
- **TCM Reactor** (Stirred Tank), which is the core of the TCES system, where the endothermic dehydration of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ takes place. The reactor operates at 130°C

during charging and it is equipped with internal stirrers and a jacketed heat exchanger to ensure uniform temperature distribution and effective heat transfer.

- **TCM Charging/Discharging Pump System**, which regulates the flow of the TCM slurry to and from the storage tanks. It manages both feeding and recirculation, ensuring optimal residence time in the reactor and smooth operation during both charging and discharging modes.
- **TCM Separator**, which performs a partial separation of the thermal oil mixture from the copper sulfate suspension before storage. This step ensures proper material consistency and prevents contamination of the stored TCM.
- **Steam storage**, which store the water vapor released during the dehydration process in the TCM reactor. This will be later use in the discharging process as additional heat input for the ORC cycle and then fed to the reactor in order to decrease the reactor thermal input during the discharging phase, increasing the process efficiency.

For the heat pump the working fluid selected is Novec649, coherent with the experimental campaign run at POLIMI laboratory on the reversible ORC/HP prototype provided by Enerbasque.

The main HP subcomponents, along with their input variables, are:

- **The evaporator**, which recovers the waste heat from the CHP unit to preheat and evaporate the HP working fluid. As already mentioned, an intermediate water loop is placed between the working fluid and the CHP exhausts primarily to reduce system complexity, particularly in the design of the heat exchanger. Moreover, since the CHP is already a cogenerative unit used for district heating, it is equipped with an existing exhaust-to-water heat exchanger, making the integration of the water loop both practical and cost-effective.
- **The compressor**, driven by an electric motor, which increases the pressure of the working fluid to the desired level before it enters the TCM-working fluid heat exchanger (i.e., the condenser). Given the relatively large scale of the system, a centrifugal compressor is considered the most suitable option for the machine. Accordingly, an isentropic efficiency equal to 80% is assumed in the model.
- **The recuperator**, which recovers the thermal energy from the hot working fluid exiting the TCES heat exchanger and transfers it to the low-pressure fluid before compression, avoiding any potential issue of two phase flow in the compressor. This component is designed with a pinch point temperature difference of 3°C and pressure drops on the hot and cold side of 0.05 and 0.5 bar, respectively.
- **The expansion valve**, which reduces the pressure of the condensed working fluid before it enters the recuperator and the low-pressure side of the cycle. This throttling process is modelled as isenthalpic.

Figure 36. IPSE GO Charging process for POLIMI Leonardo campus Use Case VI

3.3.3. The Discharging Mode

In the same way, [Figure 37](#) shows the configuration of the TCES system operating in discharging mode, as implemented in the IPSE Go simulation platform for Use Case VI (POLIMI Leonardo campus). The process models the exothermic hydration of the thermochemical material (TCM), which releases stored thermal energy upon reacting with water vapor. This released heat is subsequently transferred to an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) module for the cogeneration of electricity and thermal power for a the POLIMI campus district heating network.

The system receives the charged TCM slurry from the dedicated storage tanks. The material is then pumped into the CSTR, where steam is injected under controlled conditions to trigger the hydration reaction. The heat generated is transferred to the ORC and the discharged TCM is directed to its corresponding storage vessel for future reuse.

Figure 37. IPSE GO Discharging process for POLIMI Leonardo campus Use Case VI

Below are the main systems, their functions, and relevant input parameters for the discharging configuration of the TCES system:

- **TCM Reactor**, which operates at 125°C during the discharge phase. Steam is injected to trigger the exothermic hydration of the thermochemical material (TCM), releasing the thermal energy previously stored during the charging process. The stored steam which has been recovered from the charging process is used now to feed the reactor. More precisely, the water vapor stream is firstly used to provide heat to the ORC module until it cools down to 115°C (Steam-ORC HX in [Figure 37](#)) and then it is feed to the preheating loop before being injected to the thermochemical reactor.
- **Auxiliary Thermal Oil Loop**: Same configuration as in the charging process. It adjusts the temperature of the TCM suspension both before it enters the reactor and prior to storage, ensuring optimal thermal conditions.
- **TCM Charging/Discharging Pump System/TCM Separator**: Same configuration and functions as described for the charging mode.

Even for the ORC the working fluid selected is Novec649. The main ORC subcomponents, along with their input variables, are:

- **The evaporator**, where the reactor thermal energy is used to evaporate the working fluid of the ORC system. This heat exchange occurs between the thermal oil loop (heated by the reactor during TCM hydration) and the organic fluid on the high-pressure side.
- **The turbine**, which drives an electric generator to produce power. Given the relatively large scale of the system, an axial turbine is considered the most suitable option. Accordingly, an isentropic efficiency of 85% is assumed in the model.

- **The recuperator**, which recovers the thermal energy from the hot working fluid exiting the turbine and transfers it to the high-pressure fluid before it enters the TCM-ORC heat exchanger, avoiding any potential issue of two phase flow in the compressor. This component is designed with a pinch point temperature difference of 3°C and pressure drops on the hot and cold side of 0.03 and 0.1 bar, respectively.
- **The ORC pump**, which increase the pressure of the condensed working fluid before it enters the high-pressure side of the recuperator. The pump is modeled assuming a constant isentropic efficiency of 80%, and its electrical consumption is accounted for in the overall performance analysis.
- **DH Heat Exchanger/Condenser:** which transfers another portion of the thermal energy from the reactor to a pressurized water circuit supplying the POLIMI Leonardo Campus district heating (DH) network. The operating temperatures are assumed to be 55°C (supply) and 35 °C (return), in line with a advanced DHN design conditions.

4. Results

This section presents the main outcomes of the implementation of the virtual Use-Case VI, with the description of the Process Simulations (4.1), including: the results of the charging mode scenario; and the respective to the results of the discharging mode scenario; as well as some economic aspects of the overall simulated system (4.2). Together, these results provide insights for the technical feasibility of the proposed system.

4.1. Process Simulations

The following subchapters summarize the main process outcomes coming from the IPSE GO model simulations, under different operating modes, considering the charging and the discharging modes.

4.1.1. The Charging Mode

The data reported in Table 10 and Table 11 describe the evolution of the thermochemical material (TCM) composition and mass flow rate across the charging phase of the TCES system. The feed to the charging reactor (Table 10) consists predominantly of hydrated copper sulfate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), accounting for 70% of the total mass, mixed with 30% thermal oil. No dehydrated salt or free water is present at the inlet. Following the endothermic dehydration reaction, the output stream directed to the charged TCM storage (Table 11) shows a marked compositional shift: hydrated salt content drops to approximately 4.3%, while anhydrous CuSO_4 becomes the main constituent (58.5%), indicating successful chemical energy storage. Thus, the efficiency of the dehydration reaction during charging is approximately 95% (input parameter to the model), meaning that the majority of the hydrated salt is successfully converted into its dehydrated form, storing chemical energy effectively.

The oil content slightly increases due to mass reduction in the salt phase, and the total mass flow rate decreases from 10.53 to 8.51 t/h, reflecting the release of water vapor during dehydration and subsequent separation.

Table 10. Discharged TCM composition and mass flow rate going to charging reactor.

Discharged TCM composition going to charging reactor	value	units
Mass flow rate	10.53	t/h
$W_{\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	0.7	kg/kg
W_{CuSO_4}	0	kg/kg
W_{Oil}	0.3	kg/kg
W_{Water}	0	kg/kg

Table 11. Charged TCM composition and mass flow rate going to the TCM storage.

Charged TCM Composition	value	units
Mass flow rate	8.51	t/h
$W_{\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	0.0433	kg/kg
W_{CuSO_4}	0.5854	kg/kg
W_{Oil}	0.3713	kg/kg
W_{Water}	0	kg/kg

Table 12 summarizes the main performance of the heat pump (HP) during the charging phase of the TCES system. The HP supplies a thermal power of approximately 2141 kW to the TCM reactor through the condenser, using around 387.5 kW of electrical power input. This corresponds to a Coefficient of Performance (COP) of 5.52, coherent with annual analysis developed in Section 3. The evaporator extracts 1791 kW of heat from the intermediate water loop, equal to the maximum recoverable thermal power from the CHP (see Table 1). The compressor operates at a pressure ratio of 2.88, processing a mass flow rate of 29.2 kg/s of Novec649 (volumetric flow rate: 865 l/s at the inlet, 259 l/s at the outlet). Overall, the results are well aligned with the assumptions made in the annual simulation, highlighting the feasibility of such solution for daily storage.

Table 12. Key results of the HP (charging cycle)

Results of HP/charging	value	units
Cycle Electrical Power Input	387.53	kW
Condenser Heat to Reactor	2140.71	kW
Evaporator Heat Transfer	1790.96	kW
COP	5.52	-
Compressor Pressure Ratio	2.88	-
Compressor Mass Flow	29.20	kg/s
Compressor Inlet Volumetric Flow	864.86	l/s
Compressor Outlet Volumetric Flow	259.32	l/s

Table 13 summarizes the key properties of the water vapor released during the endothermic dehydration process occurring in the TCM reactor. The steam, exiting at 130 °C and 2.7 bar, still presents thermodynamic conditions which are suitable for heat recovery. With a mass flow rate of 2.02 t/h, the vapor stream carries a substantial amount of thermal energy. Notably, around 1255 kW of thermal power can be recovered simply by cooling the steam down to 115 °C to provide an additional input to the ORC cycle, indicating a valuable opportunity for integrating steam storage for later use. Furthermore, the steam at 115 °C can be used as input for the thermochemical reactor, significantly lowering the heat input required and increasing considerably the process energy efficiency.

Table 13. Conditions of the water vapor released during the dehydration process in the TCM reactor and going to the steam storage

Stored Steam conditions	value	units
Mass flow rate	2.02	t/h
Temperature	130	°C
Pressure	2.7	bar
Recoverable thermal power cooling down the stream to 115 °C	1255.45	kW

Table 14 presents the thermodynamic conditions of the heat pump cycle (top section) and the water loop interfacing with the CHP unit (bottom section). The refrigerant (Novec 649) undergoes a typical vapor compression cycle. The pressure rises from approximately 3.3 bar to 9.3 bar across the compressor, with a significant increase in temperature, from 129 °C to nearly 149 °C.

In the bottom section, it is possible to notice that the intermediate loop water enters the heat exchanger at 150 °C and 2 bar and exits at 90 °C and 1.9 bar, allowing to exploit 1791 kW of residual heat from the CHP flue gases.

Table 14. Thermodynamic conditions of the heat pump cycle (top) and of the water coming and returning to the CHP heat exchanger (bottom)

#	p	T	h	x	fluid
	[bar]	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[-]	
1	9.19	132.00	352.61	0.00	Novec 649
2	8.69	99.65	312.51	subcooled	
3	3.31	88.23	312.51	0.18	
4	3.29	88.00	373.85	1.00	
5	3.24	129.00	413.95	superheated	
6	9.34	148.86	425.92	superheated	
7	9.30	132.59	407.77	1.00	

#	p	T	h	x	fluid
	[bar]	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[-]	
11	2.00	150.00	2769.09	subcooled	Water from CHP
12	1.90	90.00	377.06	subcooled	Water to CHP

4.1.2. The Discharging Mode

During the discharging mode the flow coming from and to the reactor are reverted, keeping the same exact composition and mass flow rate provided in Table 10 and Table 11.

Table 15 summarizes the key performance metrics of the ORC system operating during the discharging phase. The system delivers a gross electrical power output of 162.36 kW, with a net output after accounting for parasitic consumption of 154.35 kW. The thermal input to the ORC evaporator from the TCM reactor amounts to 297.94 kW, resulting in a gross cycle efficiency of 10.45% and a net efficiency of 9.94%, which are consistent with typical performance values for small-scale ORC unit operating at relatively low temperatures and with the values assumed in the yearly analysis.

Table 15. Key results of the ORC (discharging cycle)

ORC Discharging	value	units
Cycle El. Power Output	162.36	kW
Net El. Power Output	154.35	kW
Evaporator Heat from Reactor	297.94	kW
Condenser Heat Transfer	1399.05	kW
Gross Cycle Efficiency	10.45	%
Net Cycle Efficiency	9.94	%
Turbine Pressure Ratio	3.85	-
Turbine Mass Flow	3.15	kg/s
Turbine Inlet Volumetric Flow	32.31	l/s
Turbine Outlet Volumetric Flow	783.45	l/s

Table 16 presents the thermodynamic states of the ORC working fluid and the district heating water loop during the discharging operation. The ORC cycle uses Novec649 as the working fluid. It enters the pump in saturated liquid conditions (point 1) and is then fed to the cold side of the recuperator (points 2–3), where it is preheated by recovering part of the heat from the turbine exhaust (point 7). The fluid subsequently enters the evaporator (points 4–5), where it absorbs thermal energy released by the exothermic hydration reaction occurring in the TCM reactor. The working fluid exits from the heat exchanger in saturated vapor conditions at 122 °C and 7.43 bar.

The vapor then expands through the turbine, generating mechanical power that is converted to electricity (points 6–7). After expansion, the working fluid is still in a superheated state and enters the hot side of the recuperator (points 7–8), where it transfers part of its residual heat to the working fluid coming from the pump. It finally reaches point 9, slightly above the condensation temperature, before being fully condensed in the DH heat exchanger.

The water loop for district heating operates between 35 °C and 55 °C, with water entering the condenser at low temperature (point 11) and leaving heated (point 12), thereby recovering part of the low-grade heat rejected by the ORC.

Table 16. Thermodynamic conditions of the ORC cycle (top) and of the water supplied and returning to the district heating network (bottom)

#	P	T	h	x	fluid
	bar	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[-]	
1	1.87	68.00	275.61	0.00	Novec 649
2	7.58	68.37	276.10	Subcooled	
3	7.48	93.89	305.69	Subcooled	
4	7.43	122.00	339.90	Subcooled	
5	7.43	122.00	400.19	1.00	
6	7.43	122.00	400.19	1.00	
7	1.93	102.85	390.31	Superheated	
8	1.90	71.37	360.72	Superheated	
9	1.90	68.52	358.07	Superheated	

#	P	T	h	x	fluid
	bar	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[-]	
11	2.00	35.00	146.82	Subcooled	Water from DHN
12	1.90	55.00	230.39	Subcooled	Water to DHN

5. Conclusions

The RESTORE solution proposed and adapted to the Use-Case VI was comprehensively described in this document. This deliverable has presented the design, simulation, and performance assessment of the Use Case 6 TCES storage configuration developed by POLIMI and SIMTECH within the RESTORE project. The TCES system is based on the hydration/dehydration cycle of CuSO_4 , which is charged using waste heat from the POLIMI Leonardo campus Combined Heat and Power plant. The discharging phase enables the combined production of electricity and thermal power for district heating through an ORC module.

The design of the system is carried out in the most critical scenario where the heat pump is dimensioned to absorb the entire rejected heat from the CHP plant (equal to 1791 kW), thus ensuring the system is properly sized to manage the full thermal surplus. The system configuration includes a continuously stirred tank reactor for charging and discharging the thermochemical material, coiled tubes heat exchangers for coupling with both the HP condenser (charging) and ORC evaporator (discharging), a vapor compression heat pump for the charging phase, an ORC module for electricity generation during discharging, and dedicated pumps and control valves to circulate the fluids and ensure stable operation across the daily cycle.

The heat pump designed for this use case employs Novec649 as working fluid and achieves a COP of 5.5, providing over 2 MW of heat to drive the charging reaction. The chemical conversion of the TCM features a 95% efficiency and it results in a mass reduction of approximately 19%, corresponding to the release of hydration water. In the discharging phase, the ORC module supplies 1.4 MW of thermal energy to the district heating network, while also generating around 154 kW of net electricity.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the TCES system can effectively valorize otherwise unused low-grade heat, providing flexible thermal and electrical outputs. The modularity and compactness of the daily storage solution, requiring a storage volume of only about 31 m³, make it particularly suitable for an urban context like the POLIMI Leonardo campus energy grid.

6. References

- [1] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766; RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling: General Documentation of WP5-Task T5.4 on the Implementation, Optimization, Management & Validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform, ed.: F. Dargam (SIMTECH), S. Bergmann (SIMTECH), E. Perz (SIMTECH). Published in the [RESTORE Zenodo Community](#), July 2025.
- [2] European Commission, Horizon 2020 Project RESTORE “Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Environmental sustainability of DHC”, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036766>, Grant Agreement GA Nr.101036766, August 2021.
- [3] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766. Deliverable D1.1 - Report on Requirements and Specifications of the Overall Concept (V1), ed.: Francisco Cabello (CENER), March 31st, 2023.
- [4] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766. Deliverable D1.4 - Specifications of RESTORE Use-Cases and Models, ed.: F. Dargam (SIMTECH), E. Perz (SIMTECH), September 30th, 2023.
- [5] SIMTECH GmbH, “The Process Simulation Environment IPSEpro”, <https://www.simtechnology.com/cms/ipsepro/process-simulation-and-heat-balance-software>, © 2023 SimTech GmbH.
- [6] SIMTECH GmbH, “IPSE GO: The Future of Simulation”, <https://about.ipsego.app/>, © 2023 SimTech GmbH.
- [7] SIMTECH GmbH, “IPSEpro & IPSE GO - Powerful Process and Heat Balance Simulation Solutions”, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/ipsepro-ipse-go-powerful-process-heat-balance-simulation/>, © 2023 SimTech GmbH.
- [8] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766. Deliverable D5.10 - RESTORE Replication Strategy (V1), ed.: F. Dargam (SIMTECH), E. Perz (SIMTECH), November 30th, 2023.